

The modal theory of function — problems

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WHATIF
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Why the modal analysis?

- 1 Etiological analysis (Wright 1973, Millikan 1989, Neander 1991)
- 2 Systemic analysis (Cummins 1976, Craver 2001)
- 3 Propensity analysis (Bigelow & Pargetter 1987)
- 4 Goal-oriented analysis (McLaughlin 2001, Mossio et al. 2009)
- 5 Biostatistical analysis (Boorse 1975, Garson & Piccinini 2013)
- 6 **Modal analysis (Nanay 2010)**

Argument for the modal analysis

Argument for the modal analysis (adapted from Nany 2010)

P1 1.-5. require a criterion of trait-type individuation

P2 No criterion of trait-type individuation is tenable

P3 Modal analysis doesn't require a criterion of trait-type individuation

C1 1.-5. are not tenable

C2 Modal analysis is to be preferred over 1.-5.

Assumption

- P1 is true (but see Neander and Rosenberg 2013)
- P2 is true (but see Kiritani 2011)

Claim

- P3 is false
- Even if P3 is true, C2 does not follow

But what does the modal analysis say, exactly?

Modal analysis, informal (adapted from Nany 2010, 421)

Performing F is a function of organism O 's [token] trait x at time t iff if x were F -ing at t , x 's F -ing at t would contribute to O 's inclusive fitness.

How to spell out the counterfactual conditional?

*Any theory of counterfactuals could be used to fill in the details of this definition, but, for simplicity, I will use Lewis's theory.
(Nanay 2010, 421)*

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Syntax

$$\phi := p \in P \mid \neg\phi \mid \phi \wedge \psi \mid \phi \vee \psi \mid \phi \rightarrow \psi \mid \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$$

Models

A model is a triple $\mathcal{M} = \langle W, <, V \rangle$ where:

- W is a non-empty set interpreted as the set of possible worlds,
- $<$ is a strict partial order on $W_\alpha \subseteq W$ interpreted as the comparative similarity or closeness relation with respect to the actual world $\alpha \in W$ where W_α is interpreted as the set of possible worlds which are accessible from α ,
- V is a function which assigns a truth-value to every atomic sentence $p \in P$ at every possible world $w \in W$ yielding the set of possible worlds $V(p) \subseteq W$ at which p is true.

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Notation

$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \quad := \quad \phi$ is true at the possible world $w \in W$ in model \mathcal{M}

Limit Assumption (adapted from Lewis 1973, 19f.)

\mathcal{M} is limited iff $<$ is well-founded

Closest possible ϕ -worlds $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \subseteq W_\alpha$ in \mathcal{M}

$w \in C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \quad \text{iff} \quad \mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \text{ and } \neg \exists w' \in W_\alpha \text{ such that } w' < w$

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Truth-conditions

$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash p$	iff	$w \in V(p)$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \neg\phi$	iff	not $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \wedge \psi$	iff	$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$ and $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \vee \psi$	iff	$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$ or $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$
$\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi \rightarrow \psi$	iff	not $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \phi$ or $\mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$
$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \vDash \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$	iff	$\forall w \in C_{\phi}^{\mathcal{M}}, \mathcal{M}, w \vDash \psi$

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Proliferates functions in models \mathcal{M} where $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}}$ is very distant.

A minimal version of Lewis' theory

Relatively close worlds $R^{\mathcal{M}} \subseteq W_{\alpha}$ in \mathcal{M} (see Nanay 2010, 422)

$w \in R^{\mathcal{M}}$ iff $w \in W_{\alpha}$ and w is close enough to α given E

Truth-conditions, revised

$\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$ iff $\forall w \in C_{\phi}^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}}, \mathcal{M}, w \models \psi$

This is what the modal analysis says, exactly

Modal analysis, formal (compare Nanay 2010, 422)

In a model \mathcal{M} at the actual world α , performing F is a function of organism O 's token trait x at time t iff at the closest relatively close possible worlds in \mathcal{M} where x is doing F at t , x 's doing F at t also contributes to O 's inclusive fitness.

First problem: vacuous truth proliferates functions

Vacuous truth of counterfactual conditionals (see Lewis 1973, 16)

For any model \mathcal{M} , if $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$, then vacuously $\forall w \in C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}}, \mathcal{M}, w \models \psi$, hence $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi \rightsquigarrow \psi$. Note that if $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$, then $C_\phi^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$.

First problem: vacuous truth proliferates functions

Notation

p := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t

q := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Vacuous truth proliferates functions

P1 Let F be something biologically impossible

C1 By P1, $\neg \exists w \in W_\alpha$ such that $\mathcal{M}, w \models p$

C2 By C1, $C_p^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$ and hence $C_p^{\mathcal{M}} \cap R^{\mathcal{M}} = \emptyset$

C3 By C2 and vacuous truth, $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models p \rightsquigarrow q$

C4 By C3 and the modal analysis, performing F is a function of x

Example

The heart has the function to pump acid, to digest food, to make its bearer immortal, to prevent nuclear wars...

Second problem: centering assimilates 'function' to 'use'

Centering (adapted from Lewis 1973, 14f.)

\mathcal{M} is weakly centered iff $\neg\exists w \in W_\alpha$ such that $w < \alpha$

\mathcal{M} is strongly centered iff $\neg\exists w \in W_\alpha$ such that $w \neq \alpha$ and $w < \alpha$

MP for counterfactual conditionals (adapted from Lewis 1973, 26f.)

For any centered model \mathcal{M} , if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \phi \wedge (\phi \rightsquigarrow \psi)$, then $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \psi$.

Second problem: centering assimilates 'function' to 'use'

It would indeed be a worrying consequence of my view if it ended up assimilating function to use [...]. But this is not the case. What a trait is being used for is determined by what goes on in the actual world. Function (and, arguably, usefulness), in contrast, depends on what goes on in nearby possible worlds. Function is a modal concept; use is not. (Nanay 2010, 427)

Centering assimilates 'function' to 'use'

For any centered model \mathcal{M} , if organism O 's trait x is doing F at the actual world, then whether performing F is a function of x is determined solely by what goes on in the actual world.

Third problem: malfunction entails trait-type dependence

Notation

p := organism O 's token trait x is doing F at t

q := x 's doing F at t contributes to O 's inclusive fitness

Malfunction

For any model \mathcal{M} , x malfunctions at t wrt F if $\mathcal{M}, \alpha \models \neg p \wedge (p \rightsquigarrow q)$.

Third problem: malfunction entails trait-type dependence

[A]ny theory of function must be able to account for the phenomenon of malfunctioning. (Nanay 2010, 414)

Counterparts

Organism O_α 's token trait x_α versus organism O_w 's token trait x_w

Requirement for trait-type independence

The modal analysis is trait-type independent only if $x_\alpha = x_w$. For otherwise, the function of x_α is random.

Requirement is not satisfied

For contradiction, assume $x_\alpha = x_w$. By definition, x_α is not doing F at t and x_w is doing F at t . So x_α is and is not doing F at t . Contradiction.

Argument for the modal analysis (adapted from Nany 2010)

- P1 All analyses of function require a criterion of trait-type individuation
P2 No criterion of trait-type individuation is tenable
P3 Modal analysis doesn't require a criterion of trait-type individuation
C1 All other analyses of function are not tenable
C2 Modal analysis is to be preferred over all other analyses of function

Objections

- Modal analysis trait-type dependent in cases of malfunction (vs P3)
- Modal analysis assimilates 'function' to 'use' (vs C2)
- Modal analysis proliferates functions (vs C2)

THANK YOU!

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